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**AN ANALYSIS ON THE BIG FOUR ACCOUNTING FIRMS IN GHANA, WITH A
FOCUS ON BLOCKCHAIN TECHNOLOGY IN ACCOUNTING AND AUDITING,
EXPLORING OBSTACLES AND UNLOCKING OPPORTUNITIES FOR DIGITAL
TRANSFORMATION.**

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ABSTRACT

Purpose

This paper aims to investigate the perceptions of Ghanaian accountants and auditors working in the big four accounting firms in Ghana (PricewaterhouseCoopers (PwC), Klynveld Peat Marwick Goerdeler (KPMG), Ernst & Young (EY) and Deloitte and Touche Tohmatsu (Deloitte)), regarding the impact of implementing blockchain technology in the accounting ecosystem. Specifically, it will explore the perceptions of Ghanaian auditors on the effect of blockchain on auditing processes and procedures, the potential benefits and opportunities of blockchain in the auditing ecosystem, and the challenges associated with adopting blockchain in accounting and auditing in Ghana.

Methodology

This study employed a quantitative research design, using a structured questionnaire to gather data from participants. Data was collected using a Google Form consisting of both closed and open-ended questions to gather qualitative and quantitative data. The questions were designed to address specific research objectives and were pre-tested with a small sample to refine clarity and relevance. Next, a target population was identified, and a non-probability sampling technique, such as convenience sampling, was employed to select participants. Collected data was analysed using statistical software (Microsoft Power Bi and Microsoft Excel) to perform descriptive and inferential statistics, while qualitative responses were thematically analysed to identify patterns and insights. Participant anonymity was ensured and informed consent was obtained prior to participation.

Findings

This revealed low-to-moderate awareness of Blockchain-based accounting systems. Also, there was significant evidence of the use of blockchain technology in the big four audit firms. The benefits and challenges of Blockchain-based accounting systems were ascertained in this study.

Managerial and Theoretical Implications

The results provide valuable insights for auditors, researchers and policymakers.

CHAPTER ONE

1.0 INTRODUCTION

1.1 BACKGROUND TO THE STUDY

Disruptive innovations are reshaping the business landscape as we know it. Among these, blockchain technology (BT) stands out as one of the most transformative innovations in recent times. Originally developed in 2008 as the foundational technology for cryptocurrencies like Bitcoin, blockchain has since permeated various sectors, including financial markets, information sharing, and supply chains. Recently, its potential has been recognized in the accounting and auditing fields. Blockchain, a public ledger distributed across a peer-to-peer computer network, ensures that transactions are securely stored and spread across the entire network, making the information nearly impossible to alter or falsify.

In the accounting profession, Block chain Technology introduces a groundbreaking recording principle known as "third-entry" accounting, superseding the "double-entry" system that has underpinned corporate bookkeeping since Luca Pacioli's development in 1494. Blockchain enables real-time recording of business transactions among multiple participants, stored in a computer database accessible to all involved parties. Transactions are time-stamped and immutable, enhancing the integrity and transparency of financial records.

For the auditing profession, blockchain technology can significantly reduce auditors' workloads while improving information quality and reporting efficiency through its decentralisation and security features. It validates asset ownership and liabilities, minimises fraud, and provides comprehensive audit trails, thus saving time and costs. Numerous blockchain-based solutions for auditing, such as Libra, Verady, and Factom, have emerged.

However, the adoption of blockchain technology in auditing is not without challenges. Issues related to privacy and security arise from the public nature of transactions on a distributed ledger. The complete integration of blockchain into the accounting ecosystem faces numerous technical and non-technical obstacles, including scalability, security, and suitable architecture. Despite the nascent yet thriving stage of blockchain research in accounting, its impact on auditing remains relatively unexplored

1.2 STATEMENT OF THE PROBLEM

Most existing research is conceptual and geographically limited, leaving a gap in understanding practitioners' perspectives on blockchain as a disruptive force in auditing in Ghana. Furthermore, regulators and accounting standard-setting bodies have yet to provide specific guidelines for auditing procedures in digital environments incorporating blockchain technology. Thus, further research is needed on (1) adapting auditing procedures to align with blockchain adoption and the digitalization of accounting processes; (2) the impact of blockchain on auditing work, including procedures, privacy, timeliness, and risks; (3) enhancing data and information quality through blockchain, focusing on relevance, timeliness, and completeness; (4) developing new standardised auditing procedures for cryptocurrency and smart contracts; and (5) exploring the impact of blockchain in new and unique contexts, such as Ghana.

This research is particularly relevant to the big 4 audit firms in Ghana (PricewaterhouseCoopers (PwC), Klynveld Peat Marwick Goerdeler (KPMG), Ernst & Young (EY) and Deloitte and Touche Tohmatsu (Deloitte)). For financial institutions, regulatory bodies, and accounting firms, understanding blockchain's potential and challenges is crucial for future-proofing their operations. For auditors and accountants, gaining insights into blockchain can enhance their skills and improve their service delivery. Moreover, for policymakers and regulators, this research provides a foundation for developing guidelines and frameworks to facilitate blockchain adoption in the financial sector.

In Ghana, blockchain technology is generally still in its infancy stage with limited adoption. However, in a few of the sectors blockchain technology has been applied to, there has been a positive impact.

A study by Musah et al. (2019) highlighted the way blockchain technology has reduced supply chain issues in the cocoa sector thereby greatly impacting the supply chain. The technology also presents numerous opportunities in the registration of land in Ghana, thereby resolving land ownership disputes prevalent in Ghana which has introduced clarity in the land administration system in Ghana (Agbesi & Tahiru, 2020). Mintah et al. (2020) also sees the potential for blockchain in land purchase and land title registration where all land transactions will be made

accessible to the public thereby improving transparency and minimize the risk of fraud and other land related issues.

There have also been studies of the opportunities blockchain technology presents in activities such as fund management as the technology has the potential to increase the level of confidence in data protection and simplify the process of engaging in transactions on the internet (Deka et al., 2018).

However, no empirical studies have been made regarding the opportunities blockchain technology may present to accounting and audit processes in Ghana. This highlights a gap in existing literature which this paper seeks to address.

1.3 OBJECTIVES OF THE STUDY

The study has the following objectives:

- To critically assess the perceptions of Ghanaian employees in the accounting and auditing field regarding the effects of the implementation of blockchain technology in the accounting and auditing ecosystem, particularly focusing on the big four accounting firms in Ghana.
- To assess the possible benefits and opportunities of blockchain technology to the accounting and auditing ecosystem in Ghana.
- To examine the challenges surrounding the implementation of blockchain in accounting and auditing in Ghana.

1.4 RESEARCH QUESTIONS

The following questions were underlying the research:

- What is the awareness and understanding of Blockchain Technology in the accounting and auditing ecosystem in Ghana?
- How is Blockchain utilized in the accounting and auditing industry in Ghana?
- What challenges and barriers are faced in implementing blockchain technology, particularly in the accounting and auditing industry in Ghana?
- What opportunities are available for blockchain in the accounting and auditing ecosystem in Ghana?

1.5 SCOPE OF THE STUDY

This study explores the challenges and benefits associated with the adoption of blockchain in accounting and auditing practices, focusing on the Big Four accounting firms (PwC, Deloitte, EY, and KPMG) in Ghana. The research will focus on how these firms perceive blockchain technology, the barriers they face in implementing it, and the potential benefits they foresee in integrating blockchain into their operations for digital transformation. The study is limited to the Big Four accounting firms in Ghana, which may not fully represent the broader accounting and auditing industry in the country. Furthermore, the rapidly evolving nature of blockchain technology and regulatory frameworks may affect the findings' relevance over time. The aim of this research is to give a comprehensive understanding of the potential for blockchain technology to transform accounting and auditing practices in Ghana, offering valuable insights for employees in the industry, regulators, and academic users.

1.6 SIGNIFICANCE OF THE RESEARCH

The findings of the research will contribute to the broader understanding and strategic adoption of blockchain technology in the accounting and auditing sector by:

- Highlighting how embracing blockchain technology can enhance the competitiveness of the accounting firms in perspective (the big four) in the global market. As blockchain continues to revolutionise the accounting and auditing landscape, firms that integrate this technology early on will likely gain a competitive edge, attract international clients, and expand their market reach.
- Providing empirical evidence on the effect of blockchain technology on accounting and auditing in a developing country, specifically Ghana. Insights gained from this study will be valuable not only to practitioners in Ghana but also to other developing countries facing similar challenges and opportunities.
- Assessing the potential of blockchain to significantly increase transparency, decrease fraud, and improve efficiency in accounting and auditing in Ghana.

1.7 ORGANIZATION OF THE STUDY

Chapter One (Introduction), provides a general background to the study, states the problem, sets the objectives of the study, research questions, the scope of the study and the significance of the research work which has been undertaken. It also outlines how the work has been organized.

Chapter Two (Literature Review), seeks to review relevant literature in order to situate this work within the entire body of knowledge, enhance contextualization of research findings, improve research methodology and also broaden the knowledge base of the researcher as well. Here, attention is given to examining literature from a global perspective.

Chapter Three (Methodology), entails details on target population and sampling techniques and the data collection tools that were employed.

Chapter Four (Data Analysis and Discussion of Results), presents details on data analysis, discussions, assessments and interpretation of findings from the data collected.

Chapter Five (Theoretical Contributions, Managerial Implications, Limitations and Avenues for Future Research), deals with the theoretical contributions of the study and managerial implications of the study. Also, it includes the limitations associated with the research, future research avenues and a comprehensive conclusion to the study as well as the references.

CHAPTER TWO

2.0 LITERATURE REVIEW

It is widely acknowledged that blockchain has the potential to provide substantial benefits in the accounting and audit procedures, which is fostering the growth in global adoption. As a result, it has become increasingly important to critically assess in the Ghanaian context, the opportunities and challenges blockchain presents. Existing literature have explored the various challenges of blockchain globally in diverse fields and have shed light on important opportunities that the relatively new technology presents.

The Big Four Response to Blockchain

Globally, blockchain technology is being applied to accounting and audit procedures by large accounting firms and academic institutions. According to Deloitte (2018) blockchain offers many benefits to the audit process such as verifying transactions reported by clients which would promote cost efficiency, the movement away from sample based testing to testing the whole population of transactions thereby increasing the level of assurance provided in audit engagements as well as the opportunity to perform continuous online audit assessments instead of the current procedure of interim or end of year assessments. Many other big four firms including EY (2019) make mention of the possibility of continuous auditing blockchain presents to the extent of describing the audit process in a blockchain environment as “plug-in, always-on audit”. Continuous auditing also enables auditors to investigate fraud much easier as the real-time systems blockchain highlights errors exactly as they occur, permitting rapid commencement of investigations (Deloitte, 2016; EY, 2017).

The Academics' Response to Blockchain

Existing literature have explored the various challenges of Blockchain in Ghana in diverse fields and have shed light on important opportunities that the relatively new technology presents.

The opportunities offered by blockchain have been studied in academia, with Kokina et al. (2017) asserting that through blockchain, time is saved with risk of human error greatly minimized as data entry and reconciliation requirements are no longer needed. Other papers, including that of Dai and Vasarhelyi (2017) indicate the potential for a new accounting ecosystem to be developed through the functions blockchain technology performs such as quick information sharing, protecting data integrity and programmable and automatic control of processes. Schmitz & Leoni (2019) also highlight that technology makes recording accounting data more efficient together with their reconciliation and auditing.

According to Coyne and McMickle (2017), blockchain's ability to provide an immutable record of transactions can significantly improve trust in financial reporting. Carlin (2021) explores how smart contracts, enabled by blockchain, can streamline tasks such as reconciliations and approvals, reducing the time and cost of these processes. Real-time auditing is a significant advantage of blockchain technology. As noted by Rozario and Thomas (2019), blockchain enables continuous monitoring of financial transactions, which can reduce the need for traditional audits.

These advantages further feed into a regulatory upside, revolutionizing the accounting and auditing process by reducing fraud and enhancing overall transparency. Once a transaction is recorded, it cannot be altered or deleted (Yermack, 2017). This feature greatly enhances the reliability of financial statements, as auditors can verify the accuracy of transactions in real-time without relying on client-provided data. The oversight function of the regulator is expected to be made more cost-effective.

Aside the numerous opportunities blockchain technology presents, it is not without challenges. The challenges may arise due to the fact that the successful use of blockchain mainly depends how secure the underlying environment is. As a result, there arises a new requirement for audit processes of assessing the operational effectiveness of internal IT controls. (Deloitte, 2017).

Blockchain adoption in Ghana

Emerging markets, like Ghana, encounter challenges such as inadequate infrastructure and regulatory obstacles. Golosova and Romanovs (2018) explored blockchain adoption in Eastern Europe, highlighting that factors like low technological literacy and high implementation costs have impeded progress. These challenges are similar to those identified in Ghana by Nartey and Mensah (2022), who observed that despite growing interest in blockchain, the absence of expertise limits its widespread adoption.

Another challenge relates to the scepticism surrounding the reliability and security of blockchain technology. While the main selling point used by blockchain enthusiasts is its security, concerns over its vulnerability to sophisticated cyberattacks have been raised by scholars such as Conti et al. (2018). In a developing economy such as Ghana's, these concerns are compounded by the limited cybersecurity infrastructure, which makes the adoption of such technologies risky for organisations. In their maiden study on blockchain technology, Conti et al. (2018) strengthen the security argument by acknowledging that technological sophistication of the regulator, i.e., the Bank of Ghana, is a necessary precondition for the adoption of blockchain into the finance sphere. Given Bank of Ghana's own expertise limitations in the field, it is unlikely that a campaign in favour of blockchain technology will originate from the camp of the regulator. As Boin et al. (2020) point out, without robust cybersecurity measures, the integrity of blockchain systems can be compromised, potentially leading to significant financial losses and erosion of trust.

Additionally, the integration of blockchain technology into already existing accounting systems presents a significant challenge. Pappas et al. (2018) note that many organisations in emerging economies face difficulties in adopting new technologies due to the legacy systems they currently use. In Ghana, where many accounting and auditing practices rely on traditional methods, the shift to a blockchain-based system would require substantial investment in both time and resources. Furthermore, the lack of standardised protocols for blockchain implementation in the

accounting sector exacerbates the problem, making it difficult for organisations to know where to begin or how to ensure compatibility with their existing systems (Wang et al., 2019).

CHAPTER THREE

3.0 RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

Quantitative studies were conducted to achieve the objectives of this study. The quantitative study utilised a survey sample of external auditors in the Big 4 audit and accountancy firms in Ghana: Deloitte and Touche Tohmatsu (Deloitte), Ernst & Young (EY), Klynveld Peat Marwick Goerdeler (KPMG) and PricewaterhouseCoopers (PwC). This quantitative study utilised a Google Form for data collection and involved several key steps to ensure the reliability and validity of the findings.

First, a structured questionnaire was developed within the Google Form, consisting of both closed and open-ended questions to gather qualitative and quantitative data. The questions were designed to address specific research objectives and were pre-tested with a small sample to refine clarity and relevance.

Next, a target population was identified, and a non-probability sampling technique, such as convenience sampling, was employed to select participants. The survey link was distributed through various channels, including social media and email, to reach a diverse audience.

Data collection occurred over a predetermined period, allowing sufficient time for participants to respond. The Google Form automatically compiled responses into a spreadsheet, facilitating efficient data management.

Once data collection was complete, Quantitative data was analysed using statistical software (Microsoft Power Bi and Microsoft Excel) to perform descriptive and inferential statistics, while qualitative responses were thematically analysed to identify patterns and insights.

Finally, ethical considerations were upheld by ensuring participant anonymity and obtaining informed consent prior to participation. The methodology aimed to provide a comprehensive understanding of the research topic while maintaining rigorous standards of data integrity.

CHAPTER FOUR

4.0 DATA ANALYSIS AND DISCUSSION OF FINDINGS

This chapter presents the analysis of the quantitative data that was collected with the standardized, structured survey from employees in the big four audit firms. The data collected was analyzed using the Microsoft Excel and Microsoft Power Bi and they are presented in charts and graphs below.

Fig 4.1: Bar Chart showing the familiarity to Blockchain Technology by staff and their positions in the big four audit firms

From the Fig 4.1 chart above, we can conclude that,

Almost half of the staff, that is, majority of them (about 40%) are somewhat familiar with blockchain technology in accounting and auditing. Within this category, the largest group is the Associates (23.23%), followed by Senior Associates (9.09%), Interns (6.06%), and Senior

Manager of 2.02%. This shows that a large number of the staff are familiar with blockchain technology in accounting and auditing to a limited extent.

The “not familiar” section forms the second largest group with 30%, indicating that about 30% of the total staff are not familiar with blockchain technology at all. This shows that a significant proportion of the staff do not have any insight or knowledge about block chain technology. This is made up of associates with 9.09%, interns with 12.12%, managers with 3.03%, senior associates with 5.05%.

Approximately 20% of the staff are familiar with blockchain technology. This depicts that a small proportion of the employees have adequate insight or knowledge about block chain technology. This comprises Associates and Managers which have a 5.05% each, followed by Partners, Managers and Interns with smaller or insignificant percentages.

A very percentage (Less than 10%) of the employees has extensive knowledge of blockchain technology. Senior Associates and Associates each have 4.04%, while the Directors have smaller percentages. This shows that only a small percentage of the workforce is well-versed in blockchain technology.

For experts, a very small percentage of less than 1% make up this section. This implies that a very small, negligible proportion of the employees have excellent insight in or knowledge about block chain technology. This is made up of only the partner.

In conclusion, the bar chart overall depicts that a huge number of the employees in the big four audit firms have inadequate knowledge and low familiarity with blockchain technology. The data indicates that while a significant portion of the firm's staff is somewhat familiar with blockchain technology, a substantial number, particularly among Interns and Accountants, are not familiar. There is a relatively low number of experts in blockchain technology within the firm, suggesting potential areas for development or training to enhance overall familiarity and expertise in this area. According to the data, while a significant percentage of the firms’ employees have some familiarity with blockchain technology, a sizable proportion do not, especially the interns and associates. The blockchain technology experts in these audit firms are relatively very few. This

can be an area of focus for growth which may help to explore the new opportunities associated with blockchain technology.

Fig 4.2: Pie Chart showing the type of training on Blockchain Technology received by staff

Below is the analysis of the Fig 4.2 chart:

Almost half of the staff (48.51%) in these firms have had no training on blockchain technology at all. This is a very significant proportion, which suggests that either training opportunities are not readily available to the staff or these firms take no interest in involving their staff in training pertaining to block chain technology in accounting and auditing.

About a quarter of the staff (23.76%) were involved in-house training. This type of training usually takes place in the organization where resource persons are invited to train the staff. This shows that the organization takes keen interest in developing the skills of the staff internally. Less than a quarter of the staff (14.85%) participated in online courses. Online training offers flexibility

and a wide range of learning opportunities, which might explain why a notable percentage of the staff chose this type of training.

Less than a quarter of the staff (10.89%) engaged in self-study. This depicts that some employees in these audit firms are proactive in their learning and personal development. That is, they are taking responsibility for their own personal and skills development, mostly using resources such as books, journals, articles, or online materials.

For workshop training, only 1.98% of the staff participated in this type of training. Workshop training sessions are usually intensive and focused on specific skills or knowledge areas. The extremely low percentage shows that workshop training is not preferred by the employees in these firms.

Key Takeaways:

- Very high proportion of untrained employees: The pie chart shows that almost half of the staff have received no training on blockchain technology. This represents the largest area on the pie chart. This should be an area of concern for the firms as it may indicate potential gaps in skills and knowledge.
- In-house Training Preference: The most common and preferred type of training provided to the staff who have actually had some training on blockchain technology. This could suggest that these audit firms prefer to train the staff themselves, with their own resources.

Fig 4.3: Bar Chart showing the areas in which Blockchain Technology is being utilized

Below is an Analysis of the Fig 4.3 chart:

The Financial Reporting proportion represents the largest sector in which block chain technology is being utilized with almost half a percentage, 46.94%. Financial reporting deals with the recording and presentation of accurate data in the financial statements of the firms. This shows blockchain technology's ability to provide accuracy and transparency in the financial reporting aspect of these audit firms. Overall, this helps ensure the reliability criteria for financial statements are fulfilled.

The auditing and assurance portion represents the second largest sector in which block chain technology is being utilized with 30.61%. Blockchain uses a type of technology known as the Decentralized Ledger Technology (DLT) which allows for real-time verification of transactions.

This helps to decrease the possibility of errors and fraud. This enables the audit process to be faster, accurate and subsequently enhances the reliability of audits.

The Fraud Detection portion represents (10.20%). This indicates that block chain technology is hardly used in this sector as compared to financial reporting and auditing and assurance. Blockchain's transparency and traceability make it a good avenue for detecting and preventing fraud in these audit firms. The Audit firms should consider channelling more of the utilization of block chain technology to this sector.

Supply chain management has very low utilization of block chain technology. Blockchain enhances supply chain transparency by providing a tamper-proof record of the journey of goods from production to delivery. This application is particularly useful in industries where authenticity and origin are critical, such as pharmaceuticals and luxury goods.

The least utilization of blockchain is in taxation. Even though blockchain technology could potentially enhance tax reporting and compliance through automated and accurate record-keeping, it is not extensively used in this sector. The complexities of tax systems and regulatory challenges might be the reason for the low percentage.

The data suggests that blockchain technology is primarily being utilized in areas where transparency, accuracy, and security are paramount. Financial reporting and auditing are leading the way, demonstrating blockchain's potential to revolutionize these fields by providing real-time, tamper-proof records.

However, the lower percentages in fraud detection, supply chain management, and especially taxation, indicate that these areas are either in the early stages of adoption or face unique challenges that hinder widespread implementation. Future research could explore the barriers to adoption in these areas and the potential solutions to overcome them.

Additionally, this data could inform strategies for blockchain adoption in industries that have yet to fully embrace the technology. Businesses and legislators can decide where to concentrate their efforts to optimise the advantages of blockchain technology by having a thorough awareness of the current landscape.

In conclusion, this chart provides a clear overview of how blockchain is currently being utilized across various sectors. It highlights the dominance of financial reporting and auditing in the adoption of blockchain, while also pointing to areas like taxation where more work may be needed to realize its full potential. This analysis can serve as a foundation for further research into the factors driving blockchain adoption and the challenges that remain.

Fig 4.4: Bar Chart showing the benefits that the firm experiences from using Blockchain Technology

Below is an analysis of the Fig 4.4 chart:

The benefit with the highest proportion is increased transparency, with 69.70% of the big four firms enjoying this particular benefit. This implies that these big four audit firms use block chain mainly for the transparency advantages that comes with it. Increased transparency helps improve the image of the firms overall.

10.61% of the big four audit firms benefit from enhanced security through blockchain technology. This demonstrates the ability of block chain technology to provide secure and tamper-resistant records, which is very necessary to protect sensitive information of the firms.

Cost reductions as a benefit represent less than a quarter, 9.09% of the audit firms in perspective. Blockchain can streamline audit processes and reduce the need for intermediaries, overall, reducing the total operational costs incurred by the firms

6.06% of these audit firms experience better compliance and regulatory reporting through the use of block chain technology. Blockchain can ensure that records are accurate, timely, and immutable, which is advantageous for regulatory requirements.

A very insignificant proportion, 4.55% of these firms had improved efficiency as a benefit. This may be due to blockchain's ability to automate processes and reduce the time required for transactions.

In conclusion, increased transparency is the most widely recognized benefit of blockchain technology among firms, followed by enhanced security, reduced costs, better compliance, and lastly, improved efficiency.

Fig 4.5: Bar Chart showing the challenges that firms face in implementing Blockchain Technology

Below is the data analysis of Fig 4.5 chart:

The most significant challenge, affecting 56.72% of firms, is a lack of understanding of blockchain technology. This indicates that more than half of the firms struggle with comprehending how blockchain works or how it can be effectively applied to their operations.

19.40% of firms face challenges related to implementation costs. This suggests that the financial burden of adopting blockchain technology is a considerable barrier for nearly one-fifth of the firms.

8.96% of firms report difficulties with system integration. This points to challenges in aligning blockchain with existing IT systems or integrating it smoothly into current business processes.

7.46% of firms are concerned about regulatory uncertainties. This indicates that unclear or evolving regulations related to blockchain technology present a challenge for firms considering its implementation.

7.46% of firms also report security concerns as a challenge. Despite blockchain's reputation for security, these firms may be worried about vulnerabilities, particularly in the context of new or untested blockchain applications.

In summary, the most prominent challenge firms face in implementing blockchain technology is a lack of understanding, followed by concerns about implementation costs, system integration, regulatory uncertainties, and security.

Fig 4.6: Bar Chart showing the sufficiency of resources needed to implement blockchain-based accounting

Below is an analysis of the Fig 4.6 chart:

90.41% of respondents affirm positively that there are sufficient resources to implement blockchain-based accounting while 9.59% of the employees in the big four audit firms in Ghana do not believe that there are sufficient or adequate resources.

We may conclude that, there is;

1. High Confidence in Resources: The overwhelming majority of respondents (90.41%) think that there are enough resources available to implement blockchain-based accounting. This could suggest a strong level of readiness or confidence in the current infrastructure, expertise, or financial resources necessary for such an implementation.

2. Minor Concern: A small percentage (9.59%) are not convinced that the resources are sufficient. This minority could represent a group that sees potential gaps in knowledge, technology, or other critical factors required for blockchain adoption in accounting.

Organizations may feel encouraged to move forward with blockchain-based accounting given the high level of perceived resource sufficiency. Also, the concerns of the minority group may need to be addressed, perhaps through additional training, investments, or reassessments of the resource allocation.

Fig 4.7: Bar Chart showing the perception of Blockchain Technology’s future significance

An analysis of the data in Fig 4.7:

About 92.71% of respondents believe that blockchain technology will be significant in the future while approximately 7.29% of respondents do not believe that blockchain technology will have future significance.

The large and significant majority (92.71%) of employees are positive about the futuristic significance of blockchain technology. This depicts a positive perception of blockchain's potential impact in the future. However, a small percentage (7.29%) of respondents are either sceptical or do not see blockchain technology as important in the future. While this is a minority, it indicates that there is still some level of doubt among a small number of people working in these firms.

In conclusion, the high percentage of positive perception might encourage further adoption, investment, and development in blockchain technology. Also, businesses, developers, and policymakers might consider this positive outlook when planning future strategies involving blockchain. Lastly, it may also be important to understand the concerns or reasons behind the 7.29% who do not see blockchain as significant, to address potential challenges or barriers to broader acceptance.

Fig 4.8: Bar Chart showing the key areas for blockchain’s impact on accounting and auditing

An analysis of the data in Fig 4.8:

A huge percentage (72.28%) of the focus is on data integrity and security and it represents the highest impact on accounting and auditing. This shows that the primary benefit of blockchain in accounting and auditing is seen as enhancing the security and accuracy of data. Blockchain’s immutability and decentralized nature make it particularly strong in ensuring that data cannot be tampered with, which is crucial for maintaining the integrity of financial records.

Cost reduction represents 14.85% of the impact and it demonstrates the second highest impact on accounting and auditing after data integrity and security. Blockchain can reduce costs by streamlining processes, reducing the need for intermediaries, and improving efficiency in auditing and accounting processes.

Real-time auditing represents 10.89% of respondents and it depicts moderate impact on accounting and auditing. Auditor monitoring of transactions as they happen is made possible by

blockchain's continuous, real-time data access, which promotes more rapid and effective auditing procedures.

Automating compliance represents a very small percentage, thus it may have a minor impact on accounting and auditing. Blockchain can help automate regulatory compliance by embedding rules within smart contracts, ensuring that transactions comply with regulations automatically.

Fraud prevention also depicts a small percentage; hence it may have a minor impact on accounting and auditing. Blockchain's transparent and immutable nature can help prevent fraud by making it difficult to alter financial records without detection.

In conclusion, the chart depicts that the most significant impact of blockchain in accounting and auditing is on data integrity and security. This is followed by cost reduction and real-time auditing. The lesser focus on automating compliance and fraud prevention might indicate that these areas are either still developing or that their potential impact is perceived as weaker as compared to the others.

Fig 4.9: Bar Chart showing the factors that accelerate blockchain’s adoption in accounting and auditing

An analysis of the data in Fig 4.9:

Education and Training is selected as the most significant factor, with more than half of the respondents (50.50%) indicating that education and training are important to facilitate blockchain adoption. This suggests a significant need for knowledge dissemination and skills development in blockchain technology among professionals in accounting and auditing.

The Financial Incentives factor ranks second, with 20.79% of the respondents considering financial incentives important for encouraging the adoption of blockchain. Financial support could help organizations transition to blockchain technologies by offsetting initial investment costs.

Approximately 15.84% of respondents believe that fostering collaboration among different stakeholders in the industry—such as firms, regulators, and technology providers—is key to

blockchain adoption. This suggests a need for collective efforts to build a unified approach to integrating blockchain.

The factor, clear regulatory guidelines, Regulatory clarity is considered important by 6.93% of respondents. The relatively lower percentage could indicate that while regulatory certainty is necessary, it is not the primary driver of adoption compared to education or financial incentives.

The most insignificant factor, Case Studies and Success Stories comprises only 5.94% of respondents highlighting the importance of case studies and success stories. This might imply that while real-world examples can provide evidence of blockchain's effectiveness, they are not as crucial as other factors for promoting adoption.

In conclusion, the data shows that the most significant barrier to blockchain adoption in accounting and auditing is the lack of education and training, followed by the need for financial incentives. Collaboration among stakeholders and clear regulatory guidelines also play a role, though to a lesser extent. Success stories and case studies are perceived as the least critical factor in driving adoption. The findings suggest a strategic focus on education and training could most effectively promote blockchain adoption in this field.

CHAPTER 5

5.0 THEORETICAL CONTRIBUTIONS, MANAGERIAL IMPLICATIONS, LIMITATIONS, AND AVENUES FOR FUTURE RESEARCH

The advent of blockchain technology (BT) marks a pivotal shift in the landscape of accounting and auditing, promising a digital transformation that could revolutionize traditional practices. As we delve into the specific context of the Big Four accounting firms in Ghana, this study highlights both the profound opportunities and the significant challenges that accompany the integration of blockchain in these critical financial functions.

5.1 OPPORTUNITIES UNLEASHED BY BLOCKCHAIN IN ACCOUNTING AND AUDITING IN GHANA

Blockchain's potential to enhance the accounting and auditing processes is undeniable. The introduction of "third-entry" accounting represents a paradigm shift from the centuries-old "double-entry" system, offering real-time, transparent, and immutable records of financial transactions. For the Big Four accounting firms in Ghana—Deloitte, PwC, Ernst & Young, and KPMG—this innovation could lead to a more efficient, accurate, and reliable accounting system.

By providing a decentralized ledger that is accessible to all relevant parties, blockchain minimizes the risk of errors and fraud. This transparency is especially valuable in a developing economy like Ghana, where financial integrity and trust are crucial to economic growth. Moreover, the time-stamped, immutable nature of blockchain records enhances the audit trail, allowing auditors to verify transactions with greater ease and precision. This could significantly reduce the time and resources spent on audits, enabling firms to allocate their expertise to more value-adding activities.

For auditing, blockchain's ability to automate and validate asset ownership and liabilities through smart contracts could streamline the auditing process. The integration of blockchain-based solutions such as Libra, Verady, and Factom has the potential to revolutionize the way auditors verify financial information, offering a more comprehensive and secure approach to auditing. As

a result, the Big Four firms in Ghana could improve the quality of their audit services, leading to increased client satisfaction and a stronger competitive edge in the market.

5.2 CHALLENGES ASSOCIATED WITH BLOCKCHAIN ADOPTION IN GHANA

However, the path to fully integrating blockchain technology into the accounting and auditing practices of the Big Four in Ghana is fraught with challenges. The public nature of blockchain transactions raises significant concerns regarding privacy and security. In a profession where confidentiality is paramount, the open accessibility of blockchain ledgers could expose sensitive financial data to unauthorized parties. This presents a substantial risk for accounting firms, which must balance the need for transparency with the necessity of protecting client information.

Moreover, the scalability of blockchain remains a critical issue. The current infrastructure of blockchain technology may not yet be capable of handling the vast amount of data generated by large-scale accounting and auditing operations. For the Big Four firms in Ghana, which deal with a diverse portfolio of clients and a high volume of transactions, the limitations of blockchain scalability could hinder its widespread adoption.

Technical challenges also extend to the architecture of blockchain systems. Integrating blockchain into existing accounting and auditing software requires significant technical expertise and resources. This includes the development of new systems that can seamlessly interact with blockchain networks, as well as the training of personnel to effectively utilize these systems. For the Big Four firms in Ghana, this represents a substantial investment in both time and money, with no guarantee of immediate returns.

In addition to technical obstacles, the adoption of blockchain technology in accounting and auditing is hampered by regulatory and legal uncertainties. The lack of a clear legal framework governing blockchain transactions in Ghana poses a significant risk for firms that are considering its implementation. Without standardized regulations, the use of blockchain in financial reporting and auditing could lead to inconsistencies and legal challenges, undermining the reliability of the technology.

5.2.1 The Future of Blockchain in Accounting and Auditing in Ghana

Despite the challenges, the potential of blockchain technology to transform accounting and auditing is immense. As this study has demonstrated, the Big Four accounting firms in Ghana stand to benefit significantly from adopting blockchain, provided they approach its implementation strategically and thoughtfully. By addressing the technical, legal, and operational challenges associated with blockchain, these firms can position themselves at the forefront of the digital transformation in accounting and auditing in Ghana.

5.3 THEORETICAL CONTRIBUTIONS OF THE STUDY

The findings of the study are in line with institutional theory. Institutional theory deals with how firms are influenced by the factors in their external environment including legal systems, political landscape, social, economic and ecological factors. The results from our findings throws a lot of light on how these institutional pressures influence the perceptions of auditors on the use of blockchain in accounting and auditing practice. From the findings of this research, it can be imputed that auditors in the Big Four accounting firms have a high awareness of the Blockchain Technology and how it impacts modern day accounting and auditing practices. This is so because the institutional pressures identified earlier exist in Ghana and are relatively strong enough to force auditors in the Big 4 audit firms to incorporate the use of Blockchain Technology in their day-to-day activities. Most firms being audited by the Big 4 for example, commercial banks use Blockchain Technology in their operations. The general acceptance of Blockchain Technology among the Big Four audit firms amplifies the importance of the use of Blockchain Technology hence, not using it reduces their competitive advantage.

This research has emphasised the need for auditors to effectively use Blockchain Technology in auditing firms that use blockchain-based accounting systems. The distinct characteristics of blockchain-based accounting systems make it necessary to adopt certain actions and procedures.

Among them are: understanding blockchain as a whole, assessing how reliable the system is, examining the controls and governance to determine the effectiveness of the control system, analysing external data sources to verify whether they are reliable and accurate, and lastly regularly assessing audit methodology to adapt to the continuously evolving landscape of Blockchain Technology.

From the results of this research, regular and periodic education and training in Blockchain Technology should be undertaken in addition to the previously identified strategies to keep auditors abreast with the changes in Blockchain Technology.

Auditors will benefit from this research because the effective use of Blockchain Technology will expose them to several opportunities identified previously, in addition to gaining new clients and maintaining existing ones. Additionally, there could be collaboration between audit firms and professional bodies such as The Institute of Chartered Accountants, Ghana (ICAG). The collaboration between the professional body and the Big 4 audit firms in Ghana could help address some of the challenges they face in the use of Blockchain Technology.

5.4 MANAGERIAL IMPLICATIONS AND STRATEGIC RECOMMENDATIONS FOR THE BIG FOUR FIRMS IN GHANA

Given the opportunities and challenges identified in this study, the Big Four accounting firms in Ghana must adopt a strategic approach to blockchain adoption. First, firms should invest in research and development to better understand the technical, legal, and operational implications of blockchain technology. By doing so, they can develop customized solutions that address the specific needs and challenges of their clients while ensuring compliance with local and international regulations.

Collaboration with blockchain experts and technology providers is also crucial. By partnering with firms that specialize in blockchain development, the Big Four can gain access to the latest innovations and best practices in blockchain implementation. This collaboration could also extend

to forming industry-wide alliances to advocate for the development of a legal framework that supports the use of blockchain in accounting and auditing.

Training and education are equally important. The successful integration of blockchain technology requires a workforce that is knowledgeable and skilled in its application. The Big Four firms in Ghana should prioritize the continuous education and upskilling of their employees to ensure they are equipped to leverage blockchain technology effectively. This could include offering specialized training programs, workshops, and certifications in blockchain technology and its applications in accounting and auditing.

Moreover, firms should consider a phased approach to blockchain adoption. Instead of attempting to overhaul their entire accounting and auditing processes at once, the Big Four can begin by implementing blockchain in specific areas where it offers the most immediate benefits. For example, starting with the automation of audit trails or the use of smart contracts in specific transactions could provide valuable insights and experience, paving the way for broader implementation in the future.

5.5 LIMITATIONS UNDERPINNING THE RESEARCH

This research faced quite a number of limitations that should be taken into account in future research. To begin with, the non-random sampling method used in the study may have increased the risk of barriers and reduced the reliability of the findings.

Additionally, the use of Likert scale questionnaires is limited in its ability to provide an ideal or proper interpretation of the respondents' perspectives and opinions, and may not capture the full variability in their answers, leading to a skewed distribution of responses that may not accurately reflect their true opinions.

Moreover, the presence of response style differences, where some respondents consistently choose the same response category despite the content of the question, can obscure the true validity of the respondents' opinions.

The study may also have been affected by social desirability bias, where respondents answered in a manner they believed was socially acceptable rather than providing their true opinion, leading to the over-reporting of socially desirable answers and distorting the results.

5.6 FUTURE RESEARCH AVENUES

Subsequent studies could explore the ways in which internal and external auditors might modify their audit procedures and techniques in order to efficiently evaluate the accuracy, security, and integrity of blockchain-based transactions. Additionally, researchers could develop and evaluate robust assurance frameworks that can be used by auditors to assess the reliability and trustworthiness of blockchain-based systems and transactions. Comparative studies between organisations that have adopted blockchain technology and those that have not would also provide valuable insights into the impact on accounting and auditing processes, as well as the challenges and benefits experienced. Researchers could also explore the perspectives and concerns of various stakeholders, such as regulators, policymakers, and industry professionals, regarding the integration of blockchain technology in accounting and auditing practices. The evolving skill requirements and training needs for accounting and auditing professionals to effectively adapt to the changing landscape of blockchain-based technologies could also be examined. Finally, future research can focus on how regulatory bodies can develop standards and guidelines for financial reporting within blockchain-based accounting systems to enhance compliance and reliability of financial reporting.

5.7 CONCLUSION

In conclusion, while the journey to full blockchain adoption in the Big Four accounting firms in Ghana may be complex and challenging, the rewards of enhanced transparency, efficiency, and security in financial reporting and auditing make it a worthwhile endeavour. As blockchain technology continues to evolve, it will undoubtedly play a pivotal role in shaping the future of the accounting and auditing professions, not just in Ghana but globally. The Big Four firms that successfully navigate the challenges and seize the opportunities presented by blockchain will not

only enhance their competitive advantage but also contribute to the overall development and integrity of the financial systems in which they operate.

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